

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Data Inventory

Deliverable D7.6

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<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

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History of changes

Version	Date	Description	Authors (A) & Reviewers (R)
1	25 October 2023	First version delivered to the European Commission.	As listed on the second page.
2	10 October 2024	Revision after the 1 st EC review, comments of the reviewers have been addressed: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The scope of the document has been integrated. 2) The section on “Making Data available to the OCEAN:ICE community” has been revised to by removing redundant information and adding new information. 3) Section 4 Impacts has been added. Delivery to the European Commission.	A: Mariacclaudia Paolini (ETT) R: C. Bearzotti (DMI)

List of Acronyms

AABW	Antarctic bottom water
AANCHOR	All Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and innovation
AAPP	Australian Antarctic Program Partnership
ACC	Antarctic Circumpolar Current
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AIS	Antarctic Ice Sheet
AMOC	Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation
ApRES	Autonomous Phase-sensitive Radio Echo Sounder
AUV	Autonomous underwater vehicle
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum Fur Polar- Und Meeresforschung
AWS	Automatic weather stations
BSH	Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring System
CNRS	Centre National De La Recherche Scientifique
CNRS-IGE	Centre national de la recherche scientifique - Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement
DACs	Data archive centres
DATAMEQ	Data Management, Exchange and Quality Working Group
DFFE	Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital object identifier
DU	Dissemination Unit
ECMWF	European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EDMERP	European Directory of Marine Environmental Research Projects
EDMO	European Directory of Marine Organisations
EF	Environmental Monitoring Facilities
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPCO	European Polar Coordination Office
ESA	European Space Agency
ESMs	Earth System Model
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, re-usable
FESOM	Finite-Element/volumE Sea ice-Ocean Model
FOSS	Free and open-source software
GCM	Generic Conceptual Model
GNOS	GeoNetwork open-source
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
INS	In situ
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IODE	International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ITGC	International Thwaites Glacier Collaboration
JARE	Japanese Antarctic Research Expedition

JRC	Joint Research Centre
NEMO	Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NMO	Numerical models
NORCE	Norwegian Research Centre
NorESM	Norwegian Earth System Model
NPI	Norwegian Polar Institute
O&M	Observations and Measurements
OBP	Ocean best practices
OCG	Observation Coordination Group
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OF	Oceanographic Geographical Features
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor IDentifier
PISM-MOM	Parallel Ice Sheet Model-Modular Ocean Model
RCM	Real climate model
SAMBA	South Atlantic MOC Basin-wide Array
SAON	Sustaining Arctic Observing Network
SEANOE	Sea Open Scientific Data Publication
SLR	Sea level rise
SMB	Surface mass balance
SMOS	Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity
SR	Sea Regions
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SSP	Shared socio-economic pathway
TICs	Turbulence instrument clusters
TipMip	Tipping Element Model Intercomparison Project
UGOT	University of Gothenburg
UKESM	The UK Earth System Modelling project
UKRI-BAS	United Kingdom Research and Innovation - British Antarctic Survey
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNIVBRIS	University of Bristol
UNN	University of Northumbria at Newcastle
UOS	University of Southampton
UREAD	University of Reading
VM	Virtual machine
WAF	Web Accessible Folder
WOA	World Ocean Assessment
WP	Work package

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1. Publishable summary

The objective of OCEAN:ICE is to assess the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes studying their influence on sea level rise, deep water formation, ocean circulation and climate. OCEAN:ICE uses a combination of old and new observations and numerical models. For achieving this objective, OCEAN:ICE has planned a set of quasi-simultaneous circumpolar observations over periods of several years, for the period from 2022 to 2024. Old and new data are both in situ and remote sensing observations. New observations will be addressed in circumpolar and Atlantic areas to reduce currents gaps. Notably, the availability and accessibility of in situ data is not always easy and often the sources are lacking compliance to international standards, and one role of OCEAN:ICE WP7 “Data Management” is to develop procedure to unlock these data. One specific OCEAN:ICE objective in WP1 “ Subpolar circulation, heat delivery and water mass export” is to update the previous work Schmidtko et al 2014 (Link: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270161785_Schmidt_et_al_2014_final), include more data type (e.g., CTD, profilers, animal bourn instruments), include past decade observation to cover the period from 1950 to now and revise the package every year of the OCEAN:ICE project. Unlocking data means having these data FAIR-available into the main marine data infrastructures, which, for OCEAN:ICE, are SOOS, EMODnet, and Copernicus.

The OCEAN:ICE WP7 is taking over the legacy of the Horizon 2020 SO-CHIC project and is going to contribute to making Southern Ocean data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, long-term. The ingestion/standardization activities in WP7 are targeting in situ data. OCEAN:ICE supports the development of the SOOSmap (www.soosmap.aq) and facilitates data to flow towards this system, as the SOOSmap is consuming data from the main data integrators. The present deliverable indicates if a dataset is already available in the SOOS system and enables us all to see progress in coming years.

The current inventory lists also some important base layers and community reference products (e.g., GLORYS12V1 - global ocean eddy-resolving (1/12° horizontal resolution, 50 vertical levels) and the reanalysis covering the altimetry (1993 onward) – developed by CMEMS. (Meta)data will be ingested

2. Scope of the document

Timely, free and unrestricted exchange of oceanographic observational data is essential for understanding the oceans' complex role in the weather and the climate, for empowering decision makers with evidence-based information for sustainable management of the ocean and environment etc. The availability and accessibility of in situ data is not always easy and often the sources are lacking compliance to international standards, and many challenges still exist associated with good management of ocean data, such as using different formats, wide diversity of datasets, and disparate data management structures, among others (Tanhua et al., 2019).

This deliverable presents a comprehensive review of existing data sets in the Southern Ocean and pertaining to ice sheet variables used in OCEAN:ICE, with the aim of standardizing and releasing these data, ensuring that they are FAIR compliant and made available in major marine data infrastructures such as SOOS, EMODnet and Copernicus. The deliverable also describes how to access these data, including links to sources, and presents a simplified data ingestion procedure to facilitate data exchange across the OCEAN:ICE community and stakeholders.

Disclaimer: The core deliverable is a comprehensive multiparametric data inventory table for the Antarctic Ice Sheet and the Southern Ocean. The review will be repeated annually to keep the data inventory up to date from 1950 to the present.

3. Data Inventory

Basic Layers

N	Name	Par. Selection	Link to source	Description	License	Citation	Available in SOOSmap
1	CAMLR Areas, Subareas and Divisions	Topo Layers	https://www.ccamlr.org/en/organisation/convention-area	Administrative boundaries for the Commission on the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources.	CC-BY	CCAMLR. Map of the CAMLR Convention Area. Last updated October 2017. www.ccamlr.org/node/86816	YES
3	Rock outcrop	Topo Layers	https://www.addscar.org/home/add7	Seamless dataset for Antarctic rock outcrop, applicable to all zoom levels. A compendium of two polygon datasets that should display well at all zoom levels. Compiled from a variety of mapping and remote sensing sources. Medium resolution data have generalisations of 100 m, applied using ArcGIS. This dataset should be regarded as a legacy dataset as in most places it has been superseded by the more accurate rock outcrop from Landsat8. However, as some small areas of the dataset are incomplete or still of poor quality, this dataset is still of use and should be used to check the validity of the automatically generated Landsat8 outcrop.	CC-BY	Seamless dataset for Antarctic rock outcrop, applicable to all zoom levels. A compendium of two polygon datasets that should display well at all zoom levels. Compiled from a variety of mapping and remote sensing sources. Medium resolution data have generalisations of 100 m, applied using ArcGIS. This dataset should be regarded as a legacy dataset as in most places it has been superseded by the more accurate rock outcrop from Landsat8. However, as some small areas of the dataset are incomplete or still of poor quality, this dataset is still of use and should be used to check the validity of the automatically generated Landsat8 outcrop.	YES
4	Rock outcrop (from Landsat 8)	Topo Layers	https://www.addscar.org/home/add8	A rock outcrop dataset for Antarctica, automatically extracted from Landsat-8 satellite imagery. The dataset (from the below paper) has been manually edited in places to match updated coastlines and correct certain errors. "An automated methodology for differentiating rock from snow, clouds and sea in Antarctica from Landsat 8 imagery: a new rock outcrop map and area estimation for the entire Antarctic continent", published in The Cryosphere 01 August 2016 (http://www.the-cryosphere.net/10/1665/2016/tc-10-1665-2016.html). This work is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 License.	CC-BY	Burton-Johnson, A., Black, M., Fretwell, P. T., and Kaluza-Gilbert, J. (2016). An automated methodology for differentiating rock from snow, clouds and sea in Antarctica from Landsat 8 imagery: a new rock outcrop map and area estimation for the entire Antarctic continent, The Cryosphere, 10, 1665–1677. https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-10-1665-2016	YES
5	Place-names	Topo Layers	https://gis.ccamlr.org/	Compendium of SCUFN marine names (2014), and selected terrestrial ones from SCAR Composite Gazetteer (2014).	CC-BY	SCAR promotes free and unrestricted access to Antarctic data and information by promoting open and accessible archiving practices. https://www.scar.org/scar-library/reports-and-bulletins/scar-reports/2717-scar-report-39/	YES
6	CEMP Sites	Topo Layers	https://www.ccamlr.org/en/organisation/convention-area	The Convention on the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources Ecosystem Monitoring Programme (CEMP) is a program set up in 1985 by the Convention on the Conservation	CC-BY	N.A.	YES

				of Antarctic Marine Living Resources to monitor and record fishing and harvesting of marine life in and around Antarctica.			
7	Polar Front Positions	Topo Layers	https://gis.ccamlr.org/	<p>Southern Antarctic Circumpolar Current Front (sACCF) - Orsi A. H., Whitworth III T., Nowlin Jr W. D. (1995). On the meridional extent and fronts of the Antarctic circumpolar current. Deep-Sea Research Part I-Oceanographic Research Papers, 42(5), 641-673.</p> <p>Polar Front (PF) - Moore J. K., Abbott M. R., Richman J. G. (1997). Variability in the location of the Antarctic Polar Front (90 degrees-20 degrees W) from satellite sea surface temperature data. Journal of Geophysical Research-Oceans, 102(13), 27825-27833. Modified in SG region - Trathan P. N., Brandon M. A., Murphy E. J., Thorpe S. E. (2000). Transport and structure within the Antarctic Circumpolar Current to the north of South Georgia. Geophysical Research Letters, 27(12), 1727-1730.</p> <p>Subantarctic Front (SAF) - Orsi A. H., Whitworth III T., Nowlin Jr W. D. (1995). On the meridional extent and fronts of the Antarctic circumpolar current. Deep-Sea Research Part I-Oceanographic Research Papers, 42(5), 641-673.</p> <p>Southern boundary of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current - Orsi A. H., Whitworth III T., Nowlin Jr W. D. (1995). On the meridional extent and fronts of the Antarctic circumpolar current. Deep-Sea Research Part I-Oceanographic Research Papers, 42(5), 641-673.</p>	CC-BY	<p>Southern Antarctic Circumpolar Current Front (sACCF) - Orsi A. H., Whitworth III T., Nowlin Jr W. D. (1995). On the meridional extent and fronts of the Antarctic circumpolar current. Deep-Sea Research Part I-Oceanographic Research Papers, 42(5), 641-673.</p> <p>Polar Front (PF) - Moore J. K., Abbott M. R., Richman J. G. (1997). Variability in the location of the Antarctic Polar Front (90 degrees-20 degrees W) from satellite sea surface temperature data. Journal of Geophysical Research-Oceans, 102(13), 27825-27833. Modified in SG region - Trathan P. N., Brandon M. A., Murphy E. J., Thorpe S. E. (2000). Transport and structure within the Antarctic Circumpolar Current to the north of South Georgia. Geophysical Research Letters, 27(12), 1727-1730.</p> <p>Subantarctic Front (SAF) - Orsi A. H., Whitworth III T., Nowlin Jr W. D. (1995). On the meridional extent and fronts of the Antarctic circumpolar current. Deep-Sea Research Part I-Oceanographic Research Papers, 42(5), 641-673.</p> <p>Southern boundary of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current - Orsi A. H., Whitworth III T., Nowlin Jr W. D. (1995). On the meridional extent and fronts of the Antarctic circumpolar current. Deep-Sea Research Part I-Oceanographic Research Papers, 42(5), 641-673.</p>	YES
8	Real time ice extension	Ice Layers	https://catalogue.emodnet-physics.eu/geonet-work/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/52182937602db451d437bb8e82f48366b4a8dd00	Boundaries of sea ice with ice concentration between 70 and 100% - The boundaries are processed in near real time from EMODnet Physics on CMEMS OSI product	CC-BY	http://osisaf.met.no/docs/osisaf_cdp2_ss2_pum_sea-ice-conc-reproc_v2p2.pdf https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00136	YES
9	Sub-Antarctic coastline	Coastlines	https://www.naturalearthdata.com/	Coastline for area between 50°S and 60°S. South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands taken from the South Georgia GIS (https://sggis.gov.gs/). All other data from Natural Earth 'Land'	CC-BY	https://www.naturalearthdata.com/about/terms-of-use/	YES

				and 'Minor Islands' v4.1.0 1:10m scale shapefiles (https://www.naturalearthdata.com/).			
10	Coastal change	Coastlines	https://www.add.scar.org/home/add7	The dataset records ice coast and ice shelf front positions and hence change for the period 1843 to 2008. Archival maps, aerial photographs and satellite images of the Antarctic Peninsula were used to reveal the past shape of the ice coastline.	CC-BY	Cook, A., Fox, A., & Thomson, J. (2021). Coastal change data for the Antarctic Peninsula region, 1843 to 2008 (Version 1.0) [Data set]. NERC EDS UK Polar Data Centre. https://doi.org/10.5285/07727663-9B94-4069-A486-67E4D82177D3	YES
11	Natural Earth Bathymetry	Bathymetries	https://catalogue.emodnet-physics.eu/geonet-work/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/8d17218162cfa0165db357fb8e3f728f3bf321f5/formatters/xsl-view?root=div&view=advanced	Natural Earth features 5 types of raster files at 1:10 million-scale to suit your bandwidth and content focus. Two versions of the 10 million-scale raster data are offered: high resolution files at 21,600 x 10,800 pixels and low resolution at 16,200 x 8,100.	CC-BY	Natural Earth features 5 types of raster files at 1:10 million-scale to suit your bandwidth and content focus. Two versions of the 10 million-scale raster data are offered: high resolution files at 21,600 x 10,800 pixels and low resolution at 16,200 x 8,100.	YES
12	High Resolution Bathymetry	Bathymetries	https://ibcso.org/current_version/	High Resolution Bathymetry - The digital bathymetric model (DBM) of IBCSO Version 2 has a 500m x 500m resolution based on a polar stereographic projection (EPSG: 9354) for the area south of 50°S. It is publicly available together with a digital chart for printing.	CC-BY	Dorschel, Boris; Hehemann, Laura; Viquerat, Sacha; Warnke, Fynn; Dreutter, Simon; Schulze Tenberge, Yvonne; Accetella, Daniela; An, Lu; Barrios, Felipe; Bazhenova, Evgenia A; Black, Jenny; Bohoyo, Fernando; Davey, Craig; de Santis, Laura; Escutia Dotti, Carlota; Fremand, Alice C; Fretwell, Peter T; Gales, Jenny A; Gao, Jinyao; Gasperini, Luca; Greenbaum, Jamin S; Henderson Jencks, Jennifer; Hogan, Kelly A; Hong, Jong Kuk; Jakobsson, Martin; Jensen, Laura; Kool, Johnathan; Larin, Sergey; Larter, Robert D; Leitchenkov, German L; Loubrieu, Benoit; Mackay, Kevin; Mayer, Larry; Millan, Romain; Morlighem, Mathieu; Navidad, Francisco; Nitsche, Frank-Oliver; Nogi, Yoshifumi; Pertuisot, Cécile; Post, Alexandra L; Pritchard, Hamish D; Purser, Autun; Rebesco, Michele; Rignot, Eric; Roberts, Jason L; Rovere, Marzia; Ryzhov, Ivan; Sauli, Chiara; Schmitt, Thierry; Silvano, Alessandro; Smith, Jodie E; Snaith, Helen; Tate, Alex; Tinto, Kirsty; Vandenbossche, Philippe; Weatherall, Pauline; Wintersteller, Paul; Yang, Chunguo; Zhang, Tao; Arndt, Jan Erik (2022). The International Bathymetric Chart of the Southern Ocean Version 2 (IBCSO v2). PANGAEA. https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.937574	YES
13	Hillshade and bathymetry	Bathymetries	https://www.add.scar.org/home/add7	Antarctic hillshade and bathymetry south of 60°S. Hillshade created from the Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica (REMA) 100 m and 200 m datasets with an	CC-BY	REMA: Howat, I. M., Porter, C., Smith, B. E., Noh, M.-J., and Morin, P. (2019). The Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica, The Cryosphere, 13, 665-674. https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-13-665-2019	YES

				<p>exaggeration factor of 4. Bathymetry from GEBCO2019 global dataset.</p> <p>Available from: REMA - https://www.pgc.umn.edu/data/rema/ GEBCO - https://www.gebco.net/</p>		<p>GEBCO Compilation Group (2019). The GEBCO_2019 Grid. https://doi.org/10.5285/836f016a-33be-6ddc-e053-6c86abc0788e</p>	
14	Bed elevation	Bathymetries	https://www.add.scar.org/home/add7	<p>Layer group consisting of a Digital Elevation Model of the surface of Antarctica (REMA) styled with a hillshade, and bathymetry from GEBCO2019.</p> <p>Available from: REMA - https://www.pgc.umn.edu/data/rema/ GEBCO - https://www.gebco.net/</p>	CC-BY	<p>200 m filled version of the Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica (REMA). Howat, I. M., Porter, C., Smith, B. E., Noh, M.-J., Morin, P. (2019). The Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica, The Cryosphere, 13, 665-674. https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-13-665-2019 GEBCO Compilation Group (2019). The GEBCO_2019 Grid. https://doi.org/10.5285/836f016a-33be-6ddc-e053-6c86abc0788e</p>	YES
15	Bed elevation	Bathymetries	https://www.add.scar.org/home/add7	<p>Composite DEM and hillshade of BedMachine version 1 (full available extent) and GEBCO2019, extending the dataset to 50S.</p> <p>Available from: BedMacinhe - https://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-0756/versions/1 GEBCO - https://www.gebco.net/</p>	CC-BY.	<p>Morlighem, M. (2019). MEaSUREs BedMachine Antarctica, Version 1. [bed elevation]. Boulder, Colorado USA. NASA National Snow and Ice Data Center Distributed Active Archive Center. https://doi.org/10.5067/C2GFER6PTOS4 . [Accessed 19/04/2020]. GEBCO Compilation Group (2019). The GEBCO_2019 Grid. https://doi.org/10.5285/836f016a-33be-6ddc-e053-6c86abc0788e</p>	YES
16	LIMA satellite image	Bathymetries	https://lima.usgs.gov/access.php	<p>LIMA satellite image - The Landsat Image Mosaic of Antarctica (LIMA) is seamless and virtually cloudless. LIMA is the most geometrically accurate (within a pixel - 30 meters by 30 meters of land) mosaic of Antarctica and has the highest spatial resolution. The mosaics and all of the LIMA products, along with previous Antarctic mosaics, can be downloaded at no charge</p>	CC-BY	<p>Bindschadler, R., Vornberger, P., Fleming, A., Fox, A., Mullins, J., Binnie, D., Paulson, S., Granneman, B., Gorodetzky, D., (2008). The Landsat Image Mosaic of Antarctica. Remote Sensing of Environment, 112, pp. 4214-4226. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2008.07.006</p>	YES
17	MODIS satellite image	Bathymetries	https://nsidc.org/data/iceshelves/images/	<p>Changes in the extent and stability of Antarctic ice shelves prompted NSIDC to begin a monitoring program of the major ice streams and outlet glaciers along the Antarctic coast. This archive spans back to the late 1980s. We began by using data from the AVHRR Polar 1 km data set and in 2001 switched to MODIS Level-1B data. Most of the Antarctic coastline is being monitored year-round. This archive is a selected subset of scenes, generally the clearest and most informative scenes available.</p>	CC-BY	<p>Scambos, T., J. Bohlander, B. Raup (1996). Images of Antarctic Ice Shelves. [indicate subset used]. Boulder, Colorado USA: National Snow and Ice Data Center. http://dx.doi.org/10.7265/N5NC5Z4N</p>	YES

Reference Data

N	Name	Type	Link to source	Description	Citations	Available in SOOSmap
1	Absolute Sea Level Trend	Reanalysis for Climate	https://prod-geonetwork.emodnet-physics.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search#/metadata/EMODNET_SEA_LEVEL_TREND	Global Sea Level Trend (1993-2018) - This product integrates sea level from satellite altimetry data averaged over the whole period and over calendar months, and in situ sea level data from the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (Revised Local Reference). Sea level trend is presented in false colour, while solid dots indicate in situ platforms.	N.A.	YES
2	Temperature and Salinity in the water column - CORA Climatology	Reanalysis for Climate	https://www.corolis.eu.org/Data-Products/Products/CORA/If-you-use-the-CORA-data-please-cite	Climatology (based on CORA product by IFREMER). Monthly gridded analysis fields of temperature throughout the water column from the reprocessed (ISAS software) in-situ data collections (1990 to present). The product is based on the Coriolis Ocean database for ReAnalysis (CORA) v.5.2., developed by IFREMER for CMEMS	Climatology (based on CORA product by IFREMER). Monthly gridded analysis fields of temperature throughout the water column from the reprocessed (ISAS software) in-situ data collections (1990 to present). The product is based on the Coriolis Ocean database for ReAnalysis (CORA) v.5.2., developed by IFREMER for CMEMS	YES
3	SCAR Iceberg Database	Data From Ship	https://data.npolar.no/dataset/e4b9a604-1b64-4890-9f21-56b5589807c4	In the period between the austral summers of 1982/83 to 1997/98, iceberg observations were recorded by most research vessels cruising Antarctic waters, under an international programme for systematic collection of Antarctic iceberg data initiated by The Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) in 1981 with the endorsement of the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR). The resulting database contains records of 320 493 iceberg positions from 26 601 individual observations. Of these, 259 479 icebergs have been classified by size into five different length categories: 10-50, 50-200, 200-500, 500-1000 and >1000 m. The database also includes 8061 additional iceberg observations collected by the Australian National Antarctic Research Expeditions ships from 1984 (AAD), operating in the 50-150° E longitude sector. Some of these have been classified by slightly different size categories. The dataset is described in detail in the attached data report, with an overview of the contents of the database and their potential use, the data quality and quality control process, and some concluding remarks on iceberg occurrence and distribution around Antarctica; drift patterns, dissolution rates, calving rates and their contribution to the mass balance of Antarctica: https://api.npolar.no/dataset/e4b9a604-1b64-4890-9f21-56b5589807c4/ file/4c06b3bb9d2ef3dc8933085ba6d6bbff8	Orheim, O., Giles, B., Moholdt, G., Jacka, J., Bjørndal, A. (2021). The SCAR International Iceberg Database [Data set]. Norwegian Polar Institute. https://doi.org/10.21334/npolar.2021.e4b9a604	YES

4	Sea floor potential temperature - GLORYS12V1	Model	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030/description	Daily mean fields from Global Ocean Physics Analysis - GLORYS12V1 - Based on the global forecasting CMEMS system by MERCATOR Ocean	Daily mean fields from Global Ocean Physics Analysis - GLORYS12V1 - Based on the global forecasting CMEMS system by MERCATOR Ocean	YES
5	NOAA Optimum Interpolation (OI) SST V2 (sst.mnmean), 1.0°, 1981-present	Reanalysis for Climate	https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.noaa.oisst.v2.html	The NOAA OI.v2 SST monthly fields are derived by a linear interpolation of the weekly optimum interpolation (OI) version 2 fields to daily fields then averaging the daily values over a month. The monthly fields are in the same format and spatial resolution as the weekly fields. The ice field shows the approximate monthly average of the ice concentration values input to the SST analysis. Ice concentration is stored as the percentage of area covered. For the ice fields, the land and coast grid cells have been set to the netCDF missing value.	Reynolds, R.W., N.A. Rayner, T.M. Smith, D.C. Stokes, and W. Wang, (2002). An improved in situ and satellite SST analysis for climate. J. Climate, 15, 1609-1625. NOAA Optimum Interpolation (OI) SST V2 data provided by the NOAA PSL, Boulder, Colorado, USA, from their website at https://psl.noaa.gov	YES
6	Daily Southern Ocean Sea Level Anomaly And Geostrophic Currents from multimission altimetry, 2013-2019	Reanalysis for Climate	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00698/81032/	This product contains Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) and geostrophic currents anomalies in the subpolar Southern Ocean, including its sea-ice covered parts, from 2013 to 2019. It has been constructed by combining observations from multiple satellites, including Cryosat-2, Sentinel-3A, and AltiKa. Along-track measurements have been processed with state-of-the-art algorithms, such as neural network waveform classification algorithm, or physical retracking for both leads and open ocean for AltiKa. Measurements are mapped daily on a 25-km grid south of 50°S.	Auger Matthis, Prandi Pierre, Sallée Jean-Baptiste (2021). Daily Southern Ocean Sea Level Anomaly And Geostrophic Currents from multimission altimetry, 2013-2019. SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/81032	NO

In Situ Data

N	Name	Type	Par. Selection	Link to source	Description	Citations	Available in SOOSmap
1	AADC (2019) Extract of data from the sea ice measurements database - 1985-2007	Data From Ship, Fixed Stations	Sea Ice	https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/records/sea_ice_measurements_database	Australian Arctic Data Center - in-situ measurements of Antarctic sea ice and snow cover properties	Australian Antarctic Data Centre application, "Sea ice measurements database"	YES
2	AGULHAS II and S.A. AGULHAS	Data From Ship	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://catalog.data.gov/dataset/?q=AGULHAS&sort=views_recent+desc&ext_location=&ext_bbox=&ext_prev_extent=	CTD casts conducted during the AgulhasII cruise (December 2021/January 2022, S.A. AgulhasII).	Steiger Nadine, Salle JB, Ward Brian, Azevedo Alexandra, Binase Zanele, Ten Doeschat Anneke, Els Heino, Hamnca Siyabulela, Jacobs Leon, Katsoulis Michael, Lavanchy Sebastian, Lavis Craig, Lourenco Antonio, Du Plessis Marcel, Rosenthal Hanna, Soares Bianca, Spira Theo (2022). CTD observation - SO-CHIC Cruise 2022. SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/95314	NO
3	Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE)	Data From Ship	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://swisspolar.ch/expeditions/ace/ace-data/	the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE) is demonstrated by the huge variety and nature of the data collected. Simultaneously collecting data and samples from a circumnavigation of Antarctica over a period of 90 days in the southern summer of 2016/17 will give us a holistic view of the Southern Ocean and aid our understanding of this region	Thomas, J., Landwehr, S., Volpi, M. and Schmale, J. (2019). ACE-DATA: Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition: Delivering Added value To Antarctica (Version 1.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2587954	YES
4	Antarctic Tide Gauge Database	Fixed Platform	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://www.usap-dc.org/view/dataset/601358	The Antarctic Tide Gauge (AntTG) database provides tidal harmonic coefficients (amplitude and phase) for ocean surface height (tide-induced height perturbation relative to the seabed) at many coastal, ocean and ice shelf locations around Antarctica. The coefficients are provided for up to 8 tidal constituents (Q1, O1, P1, K1, N2, M2, S2, K2) where data is available. These coefficients are primarily intended for users interested in validation of tide models for the Antarctic seas including the areas covered by the floating ice shelves.	Padman, L., M. R. Siegfried, H. A. Fricker (2018), Ocean tide influences on the Antarctic and Greenland ice sheets. Reviews of Geophysics, 56. https://doi.org/10.1002/2016RG000546 Stammer, D., et al. (incl. L. Padman) (2014), Accuracy assessment of global ocean tide models, Rev. Geophys., 52. https://doi.org/10.1002/2014RG000450 King, M.A., L. Padman, K.W. Nicholls, P.J. Clarke, H. Gudmundsson, B. Kulesa, A. Shepherd (2011). Ocean tides in the Weddell Sea: new observations on the Filchner-Ronne and Larsen C ice shelves and model validation. Journal of Geophysical Research. (Oceans), 116, C06006. https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JC006949 King, M. A., L. Padman (2005). Accuracy assessment	YES

						of ocean tide models around Antarctica. Geophysical Research Letters, 32, L23608. https://doi.org/10.1029/2005GL023901	
5	ArcticNet	Data From Ship	Cryospheric	https://www.polardata.ca/pdcsearch/	ArcticNet is a Network of Centres of Excellence of Canada that brings together scientists, engineers, and other professionals in the human health, natural and social sciences with partners from Inuit organizations, northern communities, federal and provincial agencies and the private sector to study the impacts of climate and socio-economic change in the Canadian North	CCIN provides research data management services and infrastructure for the Canadian Arctic and Antarctic research and monitoring communities.	NO
6	ARGO and profiling floats	Argo	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://argo.ucsd.edu/	Argo is a global array of 3,000 free-drifting profiling floats that measures the temperature and salinity of the upper 2,000 m of the ocean. This product provides temperature and salinity profiles measured by the international ARGO programme in the Southern Ocean.	These data were collected and made freely available by the International Argo Program and the national programs that contribute to it. (https://argo.ucsd.edu , https://www.ocean-ops.org). The Argo Program is part of the Global Ocean Observing System.	YES
7	ASPeCt - Sea Ice Measurements Database	Data From Ship	Ice	http://aspect.antarctica.gov.au/home	ASPeCt is an expert group on multi-disciplinary Antarctic sea ice zone research within the SCAR Physical Sciences program.	Worby, A. P., C. Geiger, M. J. Paget, M. van Woert, S. F Ackley, T. DeLiberty, (2008). Thickness distribution of Antarctic sea ice. Journal of Geophysical Research, 113, C05S92. https://doi.org/10.1029/2007JC004254	YES
8	AWS locations	Fixed Platform	Atmospheric	https://amrc.ssec.wisc.edu/	The Antarctic Meteorological Research Center (AMRC) and Automatic Weather Station (AWS) program are United States Antarctic Program (USAP) sister projects focusing on observational Antarctic meteorological research, providing real-time and archived meteorological data and observations, and supporting a network of automatic weather stations in Antarctica.	The authors appreciate the support of the Automatic Weather Station Program and/or Antarctic Meteorological Research Center for the data set, data display, information, etc. (Matthew Lazzara, [and other AMRC/AWS staff member], NSF grants number ARC-0713843, ANT-0944018, and/or ANT-1141908)	NO
9	CCHDO	Data From Ship	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://cchdo.ucsd.edu/ https://cchdo.ucsd.edu/search?bbox=-180,-90,180,-40	CCHDO (CLIVAR and Carbon Hydrographic Data Office) supports oceanographic research by providing access to high quality, global, vessel-based CTD and hydrographic data from GO-SHIP, WOCE, CLIVAR and other repeat hydrography programs. These data are openly accessible and served in standardized community formats (WHP-Exchange, WOCE, and netCDF). CCHDO also manages public and non-public CTD data for use by the global Argo and OceanSITES programs.	supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. 1829814, and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration under award NA200AR4320278.	NO

10	CTD Profiles collection v. 2021	Data From Ship	Oceanography /Hydrography	1) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3813646 2) http://www.marineinsitu.eu/ 3) https://www.pangaea.de/?offset=400&f.method%5B%5D=CTD&maxlat=-60	Temperature and salinity profiles collected by means of Conductivity Temperature Depth (CTD) probes in the Southern Ocean	1) Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE), austral summer of 2016/2017 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3813646 2) INSTAC Copernicus Marine Services - http://www.marineinsitu.eu/ 3) PANGEA - https://www.pangaea.de/?offset=400&f.method%5B%5D=CTD&maxlat=-60	YES
11	Data Trawler	Data From Ship	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://mnf.csiro.au/en/MNF-Data	Data Trawler is a portal to query and download public data from CSIRO voyages and projects. Data types include underway, multibeam, CTD, Hydrology, catch composition and specimens, gravity, wildlife observations and sub-bottom profile data.	This research was supported by a grant of sea time on RV <i>Investigator</i> from the CSIRO Marine National Facility (https://ror.org/01mae9353).	NO
12	Drifting Buoys (DBCP)	Drifting Buoys & Sailing Drones	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://catalogue.emodnet-physics.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search;jsessionid=56442CCFBF69407F3DB5EA9ED13B7431#/metadata/73583002b77cf03103367df33c027ded1b8ebe86	Drifting buoys Sea Surface Temperature. EMODnet Physics DB of the Drifting buoys. Global collection. Autonomous measuring systems on buoys allow measurement of standard oceanographic parameters. They are the Lagrangian way of measuring the sea currents	https://catalogue.emodnet-physics.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search;jsessionid=56442CCFBF69407F3DB5EA9ED13B7431#/metadata/73583002b77cf03103367df33c027ded1b8ebe86	YES
13	DWA	Fixed Platform	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://portal.aodn.org.au/search?uuid=c117a4a5-32b8-488a-8b98-ac3b7a0abc2a	Deep Water Arrays - IMOS sub-Facility	Any users of IMOS data are required to clearly acknowledge the source of the material in the format: "Data was sourced from Australia's Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS) – IMOS is enabled by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS). It is operated by a consortium of institutions as an unincorporated joint venture, with the University of Tasmania as Lead Agent." If relevant, also credit other organisations involved in collection of the particular datastream (as listed in 'credit' in the metadata record).	NO
14	GLODAP	Reanalyses	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://www.glodap.info/	Global mapped climatologies of temperature using the Data Interpolating Variational Analysis (DIVA) mapping method. This product covers all ocean basins over the years 1972 to 2013, and provides vertically interpolated data onto 33 standard depth surfaces, and gridded by bin averaging in each 1° × 1° grid cell. This product is based on the GLODAP (Global Ocean Data Analysis Project) dataset	Lauvset, S. K, R. M. Key, A. Olsen, S. van Heuven, A. Velo, X. Lin, C. Schirnick, A. Kozyr, T. Tanhua, M. Hoppema, S. Jutterström, R. Steinfeldt, E. Jeansson, M. Ishii, F. F. Pérez, T. Suzuki, S. Watelet (2016). A new global interior ocean mapped climatology: the 1°x1° GLODAP version 2. Earth System Science Data, 8, 325-340.	YES

					v2.2016b, built with surface-to-bottom ocean biogeochemical bottle data	http://dx.doi.org/10.3334/CDIAC/OTG.NDP093_GLODAPv2	
15	GOSUD - Underway data Temperature and Salinity	Data From Ship	Oceanography/Hydrography	http://www.gosud.org/	GOSUD data are provided by volunteer contributors who are willing to build freely accessible global datasets, promote standard methodologies and agree on a common data policy. The observations are collected from different categories of platforms such as research vessels, merchant ships but also sailing ships or cruise vessels.	N.A.	YES
16	MEOP-CTD database v. 2021	Marine Mammals	Oceanography /Hydrography	http://www.meop.net	Temperature and salinity profiles collected by animal-borne instrumentation. Marine mammal data were collected and made freely available by the International MEOP Consortium and by the contributing national programmes.	The marine mammal data were collected and made freely available by the International MEOP Consortium and the national programs that contribute to it. (http://www.meop.net).	YES
17	Necklace	Fixed Platform	Ice	https://necklaceproject.com/	This layer provides time series of basal melt rates from Antarctic ice shelves from the Network for the Collection of Knowledge on melt of Antarctic ice shelves (NECKLACE) programme.	NECKLACE is a SOOS endorsed project which aims to collect a time series of observed basal melt rates from field instruments on ice shelves around Antarctica, primarily using autonomous phase-sensitive radar (ApRES).	YES
18	NORSK MARINT DATA CENTER	Data From Ship, fixed stations	Oceanography, Ice	http://metadata.nmdc.no/UserInterface/metadata-api/search?q=Scientific_Keyword%3A%22EARTH%20SCIENCE%3EOCEANS%22&offset=0	Norwegian Data Center	https://nmdc.no/datapolitikk	NO
19	OceanSITES	Fixed Platform	Oceanography /Hydrography	http://www.oceansites.org/index.html	OceanSITES is a worldwide system of long-term, deepwater reference stations measuring dozens of variables and monitoring the full depth of the ocean, from air-sea interactions down to 5,000 meters.	https://scholar.google.de/citations?hl=en&view_op=list_works&gmla=AJsN-F5yqTsOxBqb2eea7CKUcjeZB2YuG90bXcm_vUyI9-8noS4Br6NeXkpQUsttpY1wpJKGgoUOJ77eskNngDWv_hoYvDVnCepQ&user=ECLfsRkAAAAJ	NO
20	Polarstern database	Data From Ship	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://www.awi.de/en/edition/research-vessel-and-cutter/polarstern.html	PRV Polarstern is a double-hulled icebreaker operational at temperatures as low as -50 °C. The ship contains nine research laboratories for biological, geological, geophysical, glaciological, chemical, oceanographic and meteorological research. Polastern - All trajectories of POLARSTERN cruise	I think each cruise has its own citation, see https://epic.awi.de/id/eprint/56014/ as an example for a 2022 cruise	YES
21	Rolling Deck Repository	Data From Ship	Oceanography, Ice	https://www.rvdata.us/data	The Rolling Deck to Repository (R2R) program provides fleet-wide management of underway data to ensure preservation of, and access to, our national oceanographic research assets.	N.A.	NO

22	SOCAT v.2021	Data From Ship	CO2	https://www.socat.info/index.php/about/	Surface ocean fCO ₂ (fugacity of carbon dioxide) observations from 1957 to 2019 for the global oceans and coastal seas. This product is based on the Surface Ocean CO ₂ Atlas (SOCAT) database v.2021.	The Surface Ocean CO ₂ Atlas (SOCAT) is an international effort, endorsed by the International Ocean Carbon Coordination Project (IOCCP), the Surface Ocean Lower Atmosphere Study (SOLAS) and the Integrated Marine Biosphere Research (IMBeR) program, to deliver a uniformly quality-controlled surface ocean CO ₂ database. The many researchers and funding agencies responsible for the collection of data and quality control are thanked for their contributions to SOCAT	YES
23	SOCOMM - Floats	Data from floats	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://www3.mbari.org/soccomm/tables/SOCOMM_float_performance.html	The Southern Ocean Carbon and Climate Observations and Modeling project (SOCOMM) is an NSF-sponsored program focused on unlocking the mysteries of the Southern Ocean and determining its influence on climate.	Data were collected and made freely available by the Southern Ocean Carbon and Climate Observations and Modeling (SOCOMM) Project funded by the National Science Foundation, Division of Polar Programs (NSF PLR -1425989 and OPP-1936222), supplemented by NASA, and by the International Argo Program and the NOAA programs that contribute to it. (http://www.argo.ucsd.edu , http://argo.jcommops.org). The Argo Program is part of the Global Ocean Observing System	NO
24	SOCOMM - Ships	Data From Ship	Oceanography /Hydrography	http://soccomm.ucsd.edu/floats/SOCOMM_data_ref.html	The Southern Ocean Carbon and Climate Observations and Modeling project (SOCOMM) is an NSF-sponsored program focused on unlocking the mysteries of the Southern Ocean and determining its influence on climate.	Authors using shipboard data assembled for SOCCOM calibration should acknowledge that "Data were assembled or collected and made available by the Southern Ocean Carbon and Climate Observations and Modeling (SOCCOM) Project funded by National Science Foundation, Division of Polar Programs (NSF PLR -1425989, OPP-1936222)	NO
25	SOTS	Fixed Platform	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://portal.aodn.org.au/search?uuid=723a3e85-04ae-40e6-ac2a-237a93d84abe	Southern Ocean Time Series Observatory - IMOS sub-Facility	Any users of IMOS data are required to clearly acknowledge the source of the material in the format: "Data was sourced from Australia's Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS) – IMOS is enabled by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS). It is operated by a consortium of institutions as an unincorporated joint venture, with the University of Tasmania as Lead Agent." If relevant, also credit other organisations involved in collection of the particular datastream (as listed in 'credit' in the metadata record).	NO
26	U.S. Antarctic Program Data	Data From	Oceanography, Ice	https://www.usap-dc.org/data	The U.S. Antarctic Program Data Center (USAP-DC) supports investigators funded by the National	N.A.	NO

	Center (USAP-DC)	Ship, fixed stations			Science Foundation in documenting, preserving, and disseminating their research results. We provide a central USAP Project Catalog for all projects funded by the NSF Antarctic program and a Data Repository for research datasets derived from these projects. Data managed include the NSF research related glaciology data collection formerly managed through NSIDC. We register datasets in the Antarctic Metadata Directory (AMD) to comply with the Antarctic Treaty and represent the U.S. in Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) activities.		
27	WOA	CTD, bottle data	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://joa.ucsd.edu/Data_homepage	World Ocean Bottle and CTD Profile Data	https://joa.ucsd.edu/assets/documents/Data_Acknowledgements.pdf	NO
28	Global Sea Level Observing System (GLOSS)	Fixed Platform	Oceanography /Hydrography	https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/data_source_guide.php	The Global Sea Level Observing System (GLOSS) was established by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO in 1985 to establish a well-designed, high-quality in situ sea level observing network to support a broad research and operational user base.	N.A.	YES

Making Data available to the OCEAN:ICE community

As previously described, see also in the DMP, the Deliverable D7.1, OCEAN:ICE is developing a FAIR data infrastructure to facilitate stakeholders in accessing and utilizing OCEAN:ICE outcomes. Depending on the format of the datasets listed in this Data Inventory, these will be made available through at least one of the OCEAN:ICE data infrastructure service layer interfaces described in the following section.

OCEAN:ICE data infrastructure

The current OCEAN:ICE backend design considers 2 VMs: 2.10GHz - 4 Core, 32GB, running CentOS and 500GB of allocated disk size. The VMs are running Docker containers. Containers are similar to VMs, but they have relaxed isolation properties to share the Operating System (OS) amongst the applications. Similar to a VM, a container has its own file system, share of CPU, memory, process space, and more. As they are decoupled from the underlying infrastructure, they are portable across clouds and OS distributions. The most popular solutions are Kubernetes and Docker that have become the de- facto standard and dominant tool with which applications are containerized, managed, scaled and released. As anticipated, OCEAN:ICE adopted Docker that offers packages with service tools like selected data publishing services.

Figure 1: Deployed architecture.

As shown in Figure 1, the management of the access to the private area is implemented by using a selective endpoint access from a given (white) list of IP address or host and domain name (fully qualified domain name, FQDN). Connections and access from edge devices out of the list will be rejected. The

idea to design a delivery buffer is mutated from the CMEMS Dissemination Unit (DU)² Delivery buffer. Similarly, the OCEAN:ICE Delivery buffer provides the partners with virtual folders in which new data can be dropped. As described in the OCEAN:ICE DMP, a preliminary approach suggests the partners to use an internal naming convention for new datasets. This facilitates the successive ingestion step that pushes new data into the OCEAN:ICE database and the data publication tools.

As anticipated, OCEAN:ICE data publishing identified tools are ERDDAP and GeoServer, which are tools for both the OCEAN:ICE service layer (they offer application program interfaces and machine-to-machine services for internal use) and the OCEAN:ICE application layer (they offer cataloguing features and machine-to-machine tools for external users).

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² The CMEMS DU is in charge of the dissemination of the products elaborated by Production Centres (PC; MFCs and TACs), and provide the users with available products by means of several dissemination interfaces. The CMEMS DU is also in charge for monitoring overall system performances (timeliness, availability, bandwidth load, etc.).

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4. Impacts

With this deliverable, OCEAN:ICE has contributed to the achievements of the following objectives indicated in the description of the action.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers. The present deliverable indicates if a

dataset is already available in the SOOS system and enables us all to see progress in coming years. With this deliverable, OCEAN:ICE WP7 is taking over the legacy of the Horizon 2020 SO-CHIC project and is going to contribute to making Southern Ocean data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, long-term.